

Topic	Item	Checklist item description	Reported on Line
Title	1	The diagnosis or intervention of primary focus followed by the words “case report”	1-2
Key Words	2	2 to 5 key words that identify diagnoses or interventions in this case report, including "case report"	62-63
Abstract (no references)	3a	Introduction: What is unique about this case and what does it add to the scientific literature?	41-42, 56-58
	3b	Main symptoms and/or important clinical findings	44-48,
	3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutic interventions, and outcomes	48-49
	3d	Conclusion—What is the main “take-away” lesson(s) from this case?	55-58
Introduction	4	One or two paragraphs summarizing why this case is unique (may include references)	94-95
Patient Information	5a	De-identified patient specific information.	99
	5b	Primary concerns and symptoms of the patient.	100 - 101
	5c	Medical, family, and psycho-social history including relevant genetic information	99-100
	5d	Relevant past interventions with outcomes	Not applicable
Clinical Findings	6	Describe significant physical examination (PE) and important clinical findings.	101-102,112-114,168-169
Timeline	7	Historical and current information from this episode of care organized as a timeline	Given as narrative text
Diagnostic Assessment	8a	Diagnostic testing (such as PE, laboratory testing, imaging, surveys).	102-108,116-118,123-137,161-165
	8b	Diagnostic challenges (such as access to testing, financial, or cultural)	133-135
	8c	Diagnosis (including other diagnoses considered)	118-119,140-141
	8d	Prognosis (such as staging in oncology) where applicable	158-160
Therapeutic Intervention	9a	Types of therapeutic intervention (such as pharmacologic, surgical, preventive, self-care)	155-158,165-166,169-171
	9b	Administration of therapeutic intervention (such as dosage, strength, duration)	Not applicable
	9c	Changes in therapeutic intervention (with rationale)	Not applicable
Follow-up and Outcomes	10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes (if available)	Not applicable
	10b	Important follow-up diagnostic and other test results	176-189
	10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability (How was this assessed?)	Not applicable
	10d	Adverse and unanticipated events	Not applicable
Discussion	11a	A scientific discussion of the strengths AND limitations associated with this case report	196-198/not applicable
	11b	Discussion of the relevant medical literature with references .	196-209
	11c	The scientific rationale for any conclusions (including assessment of possible causes)	210-223
	11d	The primary “take-away” lessons of this case report (without references) in a one paragraph conclusion	234-239
Patient Perspective	12	The patient should share their perspective in one to two paragraphs on the treatment(s) they received	Not applicable
Informed Consent	13	Did the patient give informed consent? Please provide if requested	Yes ☒ No ☐